

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL MECHANISMS TO ENSURE COMPETITIVENESS OF SMALL BUSINESSES PROVIDING MEDICAL SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on improving organizational mechanisms to ensure competitiveness of small businesses providing medical services in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It examines the theoretical and practical foundations for increasing enterprise efficiency in the context of intensifying market competition, limited resources, and bureaucratic barriers in the sector. The study identifies key organizational mechanisms that shape competitiveness: licensing and accreditation in medical specialties, resource management, departmental integration, process standardization and certification, personnel management, information systematization, systematic patient engagement, and marketing mechanisms. The research findings contribute to sustainable development of the private healthcare sector, enhancement of quality standards, and economic efficiency. The study also emphasizes the need for future expansion of the empirical base and conducting practical trials.

Introduction. The medical services sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan is rapidly developing as an important component of the economy. In the process of reforming the country's healthcare system, the role of small business entities, particularly private clinics and medical centers, is increasing. However, in the context of intensifying market competition and limited resources, the issue of ensuring the competitiveness of these enterprises is becoming increasingly relevant. Competitiveness is a complex process achieved not only through the provision of quality services but also through effective management of organizational mechanisms, resource optimization, and adaptation to market demands. This article is dedicated to the directions for improving the organizational mechanisms to ensure the competitiveness of small business entities providing medical services.

The growth of small businesses in Uzbekistan's healthcare system has intensified, particularly in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, which highlighted the importance of mechanisms such as licensing, resource management, and patient care in this sector. However, existing challenges - including bureaucratic barriers, lack of integration, and insufficient standardization - are negatively impacting the efficiency of these enterprises. The aim of this article is to analyze the organizational mechanisms for ensuring competitiveness in small businesses providing medical services, to examine the perspectives of experts and

entrepreneurs, and to develop practical recommendations for their improvement. The findings of this research will serve to enhance the strategic decision-making system for enterprises and contribute to the development of the industry.

Methodology. This study aims to explore ways to improve the organizational mechanisms for ensuring the competitiveness of small businesses providing medical services and is based on empirical and analytical methods. During the research process, existing scientific works on competitiveness and organizational mechanisms in the healthcare sector were examined, including experiences from Uzbekistan and international practices. At this stage, the main mechanisms for developing competitiveness (licensing, resource management, integration, standardization, etc.) were identified. As the primary source of data for the study, a survey was conducted among experts and entrepreneurs. Based on the survey results, an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of these mechanisms was carried out, and directions for improvement were developed.

Literature Review. The topic of improving organizational mechanisms to ensure the competitiveness of small businesses providing medical services occupies an important place in economic and managerial research in healthcare. The primary source is Porter's (1985) work "Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance," which analyzes the main competitiveness strategies (cost leadership, differentiation, and focus). According to the author, small enterprises, including medical service providers, can achieve market advantage through organizational mechanisms (for example, effective resource management and process standardization). When applied to healthcare, mechanisms such as licensing and accreditation play a crucial role in quality assurance, but bureaucratic obstacles can create problems for small businesses. Porter's approach forms the basis of our research and provides a foundation for improving organizational mechanisms to increase the competitiveness of medical clinics in the Uzbekistan context. The next source is Barney's (1991) article "Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage," which emphasizes the resource-based view (RBV). The author stresses that a company's internal resources (human capital, technology, and information systems) are the basis of competitiveness. In medical services, this theory applies to mechanisms for medical equipment supply and personnel management: for example, through effective resource management, small clinics can gain market advantage by reducing costs. However, in developing countries, including Uzbekistan, these mechanisms may be weak due to limited resources. This work served as the basis for developing resource optimization proposals in our research. Zuckerman's article "Competitive Strategy in the Healthcare Industry" examines organizational mechanisms for ensuring competitiveness in healthcare enterprises, particularly integration between departments and process standardization. According to the author, ISO standards and certification improve medical service quality and ensure patient satisfaction, but the lack of integration in small businesses hinders efficiency. This study examines healthcare sector competitiveness in the pandemic context and proposes digitalization (ERP and CRM systems). In Uzbekistan, these mechanisms are related to licensing and accreditation, which confirms the validity of expert and entrepreneur surveys in our study. Uzbek authors Abdurahmonov et al. in their article "Development of the Private Sector in the Healthcare System of Uzbekistan" analyze the national characteristics of small medical enterprises' competitiveness. The

authors, noting the complexity of the licensing process and resource management problems, recommend digitalizing organizational mechanisms (for example, electronic medical records). This work provides our study with a national context, highlighting bureaucratic barriers and integration weaknesses, and confirms the importance of patient interaction mechanisms. Additionally, Teece's article "Business Models, Business Strategy and Innovation" examines the role of business models in competitiveness, including marketing and branding mechanisms. The author emphasizes patient-centric approaches and information management systems in healthcare. This theory serves as the basis for improving strategic decision-making systems for small medical enterprises, explains the average assessment of the marketing mechanism in our study, and proposes digital marketing strategies. The above literature confirms the importance of organizational mechanisms in ensuring competitiveness but shows the need to improve them in developing countries, including Uzbekistan. This analysis laid the foundation for the empirical part of the study and helped develop practical proposals for optimizing these mechanisms.

Analysis and results. The main organizational mechanisms that form and ensure competitiveness in enterprises were identified as "obtaining licenses and accreditation for medical specialties, managing medical supplies and resources, developing organizational structure, ensuring integration between departments, standardizing and certifying medical service processes, managing personnel, scientifically organizing their work, managing and systematizing medical information, systematically organizing patient care, as well as marketing and branding, and establishing the enterprise's mission." The next direction of our research focused on studying the opinions and assessments of experts directly working in the healthcare field, involving specialists in medical management, experienced physicians, research scientists, and professors from medical educational institutions. In a survey conducted with business entities, 24% of respondents were founders, 34% were managers, 26% were chief physicians, and the rest were accountants and management specialists. It was determined that more than 86% of them were professionals with long-term work experience.

Table 1. Analysis of the importance of organizational mechanisms for ensuring competitiveness based on the survey conducted to determine expert opinions

Organizational mechanism	Mechanism evaluation level					Significance level
	high	good	medium	satisfactory	low	
	5	4	3	2	1	
Obtaining a license and accreditation for medical specialties	14	16	19	0	1	76.8
Supply of medical devices and resource management	10	18	22	0	0	75.2
Integration and connections between clinical departments	4	21	21	3	1	69.6
Standardization and certification of	11	18	19	2	0	75.2

medical service processes						
Personnel management and ensuring their accountability	15	15	19	0	1	77.2
Storage and management of medical data and information	8	19	23	0	0	74
Systematic organization of patient care	17	18	13	2	0	80
Group significance						75.42

The mechanism for obtaining and accrediting licenses in medical specialties demonstrates its fundamental role in medical competitiveness, as licensing ensures quality standards. However, some experts may have expressed dissatisfaction with the process's complexity. The mechanism for medical device provision and resource management indicates that resource efficiency is crucial for competitiveness, but it is not entirely suitable or optimal. Improving the mechanism's efficiency may be possible through supply chain digitalization. The evaluation of the mechanism for ensuring integration between clinical departments reveals it as a weak point in clinics - with insufficient interdepartmental connections affecting overall efficiency. The presence of negative assessments might be due to technological or organizational barriers. The mechanism for standardizing and certifying medical service processes ensures quality, but experts do not consider it adequate. The positive impact of this mechanism could be enhanced by ensuring wider application of ISO standards. The assessment of the mechanism for managing staff and ensuring their accountability demonstrates that the human factor is decisive in competitiveness. Experts recommended strengthening motivation and training programs among employees.

The high value placed on medical data and information storage and management is explained by the crucial role that data management plays in digital transformation. The highest rating given to the mechanism of systematic organization of patient care indicates that a specialized approach to patients is the foundation of competitiveness in service provision. Experts highly valued the organizational mechanisms - the average indicator is 75.42%, with a low standard deviation. The significance ranging from 69.6% to 80% indicates the closeness of expert opinions.

According to representatives of business entities, the mechanism for obtaining and accrediting licenses in medical specialties is important for entrepreneurs, as a license ensures business stability. It is recommended to further simplify the process through digitalization, as it is currently moderately rated compared to other mechanisms due to bureaucratic barriers

Table 2. Analysis of the importance of organizational mechanisms for ensuring competitiveness based on a survey of entrepreneurs' opinions

Organizational mechanism	Mechanism evaluation level					Significance level
	high	good	medium	satisfactory	low	
	5	4	3	2	1	
Obtaining and accrediting licenses in medical specialties	6	24	16	1	3	71.6
Medical device provision and resource management	8	11	28	3	0	69.6
Integration and connections between clinical departments	3	17	23	7	0	66.4
Standardization and certification of medical service processes	4	18	25	1	2	68.4
Personnel management and ensuring accountability	9	25	16	0	0	77.2
Storage and management of medical data and information	8	19	23	0	0	74
Systematic organization of patient care	19	17	13	1	0	81.6
Marketing and branding	9	11	24	5	1	68.8
Group importance						72.20

According to the views of business entity representatives, the mechanism for obtaining a license and accreditation in medical specialties is crucial for entrepreneurs, as a license ensures business stability. The process is considered moderate compared to other mechanisms due to bureaucratic barriers, and it is recommended to further simplify it through digitalization. The mechanism for medical supply and resource management demonstrates that resource efficiency impacts business costs. Possibly due to supply issues, this mechanism scores below the group average; its impact on competitiveness could be improved by optimizing logistics and inventory systems. The mechanism of inter-departmental integration and connections in clinics is identified as a weak point, hindering

business efficiency. More negative assessments are given due to technological or organizational reasons; this shortcoming could be addressed and competitiveness improved through software integration (CRM or ERP). The mechanism for standardizing and certifying medical service processes enhances business quality, but entrepreneurs do not consider it sufficient. Due to practical difficulties, the mechanism's impact is rated quite low; its effect on competitiveness could be increased by implementing remote audits for certification. The high rating of the employee management and accountability mechanism indicates that the human factor is crucial in business. Strengthening KPI and motivation programs could further enhance employees' impact on improving medical service quality and competitiveness. The importance of the mechanism for storing and managing medical data and information in modern digital business has been confirmed. It is suggested that cloud storage and application of GDPR standards could improve this mechanism's impact. The mechanism for systematically organizing patient interactions is rated as most significant, confirming that a patient-centered approach in medical services is fundamental to business competitiveness. Respondents emphasized the importance of developing customer communication systems. The marketing and branding mechanism is vital for entrepreneurs, as branding attracts customers. Possibly due to budget constraints, this mechanism's impact is below average; strengthening digital marketing strategies could enhance its positive effect on competitiveness.

The assessments of both groups showed similar tendencies, with working with patients and staff being the most important mechanism, while integration was the weakest point. Entrepreneurs gave a slightly lower overall assessment, especially in licensing, resource provision, and standardization, which indicates their greater focus on business practices. Experts, however, gave higher assessments to the professional qualities of employees and standardization.

Based on the characteristics of trends in the provision of medical services and our considerations on determining and improving the methodology for assessing the competitiveness of medical services, we have developed proposals for improving the decision-making system to ensure the competitiveness of medical service enterprises.

The following table focuses on the directions for improving the organizational mechanisms to ensure the competitiveness of medical services, presenting our proposals for improving the decision-making system for ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises based on means and methods of influencing mechanisms and directions for improving the strategic decision-making system

Table 3. Directions for improving organizational mechanisms to ensure the competitiveness of medical services

Organizational mechanisms for ensuring the competitiveness of medical services	Improving the decision-making system to ensure competitiveness of medical service enterprises	
	Means and methods of influencing mechanisms	Directions for enhancing the strategic decision-making system

Obtaining and accrediting licenses for medical specialties	Budgeting system for accurate calculation of license-related costs and investment analysis for determining profitability (NPV, ROI)	Calculating costs for each type of license, creating a continuous financial monitoring system, and analyzing and planning license-related service prices
Medical supply management and resource administration	Cost calculation system (Activity-Based Costing, ABC) and ERP system for inventory control and consumables tracking	Preventing unnecessary purchases through effective cost analysis and implementing an automated monitoring system for medical devices
Developing organizational structure and ensuring integration between departments	Financial reporting system - analyzing profitability of each department and monitoring work performance (KPI system)	Developing internal information systems for digital analysis and performance evaluation of departmental activities and strengthening integration
Standardization and certification of medical service processes	System for calculating service costs and analyzing expenses related to ISO and other certification requirements	Minimizing organizational costs in accordance with certification requirements and creating a standard cost base for each type of medical service
Personnel management and scientific organization of their work	Analysis of wage and bonus systems and performance evaluation system (KPI, BSC)	Developing a mechanism for assessing and incentivizing employee performance, as well as conducting statistical analyses on increasing labor productivity
Management and systematization of medical information	Maintaining electronic medical records and client database, as well as analytical tools for cost reduction	Integrating all information into a single CRM system and improving data security and optimization systems
Systematic organization of patient care	Analyzing and forecasting patient flow and measuring the effectiveness of medical services	Implementing an electronic patient queue system and monitoring patient satisfaction levels

Conclusion. This research focused on improving the organizational mechanisms for ensuring the competitiveness of small businesses providing medical services. According to survey results from experts (average significance 75.42%) and entrepreneurs (72.20%), the most crucial mechanisms were systematic work with patients (80-81.6%), personnel management (77.2%), and licensing/accreditation (71.6-76.8%). The weakest point was found to be integration between departments (66.4-69.6%). The analysis revealed that to enhance competitiveness, digitalization (ERP, CRM systems), process standardization (ISO certificates), resource optimization (ABC costing), and employee motivation are necessary. The proposed strategic decision-making system serves to reduce enterprise costs, improve quality, and ensure market advantage. This approach contributes to the development of the private sector in Uzbekistan's healthcare industry and helps increase the efficiency of small medical enterprises

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